

Hydrogen uptake by porphyrins at the $\text{TiO}_2(110)$ surface.

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Supporting Information

Experimental Methods.

We performed Synchrotron radiation spectroscopy measurements at the ALOISA beamline¹ of the Elettra Synchrotron (Trieste, Italy). We imaged the molecules with an Aarhus microscope (provided by SPECS) at the Centro de Física de Materiales (CSIC-UPV, San Sebastian, Spain), whose experimental chamber is also equipped with an XPS analyzer for checking the preparation of the molecular films.² We employed a number of different samples purchased from Mateck that were also exchanged between the ALOISA Synchrotron beamline and the STM apparatus. We followed the same preparation protocol for cleaning

the surface: sputtering with Ar^+ at 800 eV followed by short annealing up to 1000 ± 50 K (1 min at maximum temperature), which yields dark blue samples. All the STM images were acquired at room temperature with a tungsten electrochemically etched tip. In both experimental apparatuses, we deposited molecules from boron nitride Knudsen cells at typical temperature of 460 ± 10 K for 2H-OEP and 570 ± 10 K for both 2H-TPP and 2H-TBTPP. The corresponding deposition rate is found to be in the range of $0.1\text{-}0.5 \text{ \AA} \text{ min}^{-1}$, as monitored by room temperature quartz microbalances. In the ALOISA apparatus, the monolayer coverage has been defined by recording the XPS intensity after thermal desorption of a multilayer. All of the porphyrins have been shown the saturation of the monolayer at an equivalent coverage of $\sim 2.5 \text{ \AA}$.

NEXAFS C and N *K*-edge.

We measured the NEXAFS spectra at the carbon and nitrogen *K*-edge by partial electron yield, with a channeltron equipped with a repeller grid kept at a negative bias in order to let the Auger electron of the corresponding ionization edge pass through. The photon energy resolution was set to ~ 100 meV for both ionization thresholds. The orientation of the surface with respect to the photon beam polarization (linear) was changed from TM to transverse electric (TE, i.e. s-polarization) by rotation of the surface around the photon beam axis while keeping a constant grazing angle of 6° . Absolute calibration of the photon energy energy scale is performed a posteriori by using as a reference the carbon and nitrogen absorption features detected in the drain current recorded on the gold coating of the last beamline optics (synchronized acquisition). The scattering geometry of the ALOISA endstation, as well as the absolute calibration procedure are described in more detail in Ref.³

The NEXAFS spectra in TM polarization for the monolayer phase of porphyrins on $\text{TiO}_2(110)$ are dominated by the resonances of the π -symmetry unoccupied MOs, due to the closely planar molecular orientation. This geometry is preserved also in the next few molecular layers before a 3D growth takes place. The carbon spectra in TM polarization are characterized by two main peaks (see Fig. 1). For all of the three molecules, the first resonance at ~ 284.1 eV corresponds to the resonance of the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO), which is localized on the pyrrolic carbon atoms. This resonance displays a large dichroism with a residual intensity in TE polarization of $\sim 10\%$, that can be ascribed either to a minority of second layer molecules and defects or to a small out of plane distortion of the tetra-pyrrolic macrocycle due to the hydrogen uptake. Overall, we can conclude that three porphyrin molecules display the same planar orientation of the inner macrocycle, irrespective of their different peripheral terminations.

The second resonance at ~ 285.2 eV is mostly contributed by the molecular orbital localized on the phenyl carbon atoms in the case of TPP and TBTPP, while it stems from the LUMO+1 of the pyrrolic rings in the case of OEP (with a much lower intensity and slightly different energy). While the latter pyrrolic LUMO+1 resonances displays a dichroism simply following that of its LUMO counterpart, the NEXAFS resonances associated with phenyls display a smaller dichroism, indicating that they are tilted off the surface (of $25\text{-}30^\circ$ and 40° for TBTPP and TPP, respectively). This tilt angle confirms that both TPP and TBTPP preserve their 3D structure, although slightly relaxed with respect to their bulk phase.

The nitrogen *K*-edge NEXAFS spectra, shown in Fig. 2 display a strong similarity among

Figure 1: Carbon K -edge NEXAFS spectra measured in TM and TE polarization (open and filled markers, respectively) for metal-free porphyrin films grown on $\text{TiO}_2(110)$ at room temperature in the monolayer coverage range.

Figure 2: Nitrogen K -edge NEXAFS spectra measured in TM and TE polarization (open and filled markers, respectively) on the same films of previous Figure.

the different porphyrins with a characteristic sequence of resonances at ~ 398 , 400 and 402 eV. The first two peaks correspond to the π -symmetry unoccupied MOs localized on the iminic (LUMO at 397.7-398.0 eV) and pyrrolic nitrogen (LUMO+1 at ~ 400 eV). For all the three molecules, the residual intensity recorded at the iminic LUMO resonance can be associated with the residual iminic intensity observed in the corresponding photoemission spectra (see Fig. 1 in the article and following XPS analysis). It is worth recalling that, at variance with XPS, the intensity of the NEXAFS resonances is not simply reflecting the compound stoichiometry. The residual iminic component (corresponding to the minority phase of unreacted molecules) displays a dichroism larger than that of the LUMO+1 resonance (corresponding to the majority phase of hydrogen-reacted molecules), indicating that the rings associated with the pyrrolic nitrogen are tilted off the surface by an angle larger than that of the rings associated with iminic nitrogen. This observation is in qualitative agreement with DFT calculations showing an increase of the average tilt angle of the macrocycle rings upon hydrogen uptake.

Figure 3: Photoemission spectra of 2H-TPP at 5.5 (top) and 0.8 ML (bottom). The experimental data (open markers) are taken from Fig. 1 of the article (measured at $h\nu = 500$ eV with $\Delta E \sim 160$ meV). Fitting curves are shown as full lines and resolved in single peaks. The corresponding fitting analysis is reported on the right side.

XPS analysis of the N 1s core level

We measured the VB spectra at a photon energy of 140 eV with an overall energy resolution of ~ 120 meV. We measured core level photoemission spectra of O 1s, Ti 2p, N 1s and C 1s with a photon energy of 650 and 500 eV at a corresponding overall resolution of 280 and 160 meV, respectively. We calibrated the photoemission spectra to the binding energy of Ti $2p_{3/2} = 459.1$ eV and Ti 3p at 37.6 ± 0.05 eV. All XPS measurements have been performed in transverse magnetic polarization (TM, i.e. close to p-polarization) and normal emission geometry, with the sample kept a grazing angle of 4° . Spectra have been collected with a hemispherical electron spectrometer (mean radius 66 mm) equipped with a 2D delay-line detector. The N 1s photoemission peaks have been fitted to true Voigt function with a Shirley background. The fitting analysis is shown in 3 for the case of 2H-TPP molecules at the coverage of 5.5 and 0.8 ML. The overall FWHM of the pyrrolic peak is found to be 0.69 and 1.05 eV at 5.5 and 0.8 ML, respectively.

DFT calculations.

Adsorption of 2H-TPP on the $\text{TiO}_2(110)$ surface was studied with DFT calculations using the Quantum ESPRESSO package.⁵ The PBE functional⁶ in conjunction with Grimme dispersion corrections^{7,8} was used. Ion cores were described by Vanderbilt ultrasoft pseudopotentials (PPs), which included C, N, and O 1s orbitals. Ti ions were described either by “large core” PPs including 1s–3p electrons, or with “small cores”, including 1s–2p electrons (see below). The kinetic energy cutoff of the planewave expansion was 25 Ry (200 Ry for the Vanderbilt augmentation charge). To simulate low-coverage conditions, we adopted an oblique ($\frac{3}{6} \frac{3}{1}$) supercell including 21 unit cells. The theoretical PBE-D lattice constants of TiO_2 were used.⁹

Because of the large size and conformational flexibility of the adsorbate, which requires both large memory usage and long run times, the energetics of the 2H-TPP/4H-TPP species with the TiO_2 surface was first explored on thin (three TiO_2 layers) slab models using “large core” PPs. The structure and the stability of the most favorable configurations were eventually recomputed more accurately using “small core” pseudopotentials and four TiO_2 layers. The two bottom layers of the slabs were frozen in the bulk structure. Because of the large size of the supercells, only the Γ point of the Brillouin zone was sampled. We explored the adsorption energetics considering 4H-TPP species centered on top (OT) of O_{2c} and Ti_{5c} ions and at bridging positions (BR) between two O_{2c} and two Ti_{5c} ions. Furthermore, two azimuthal orientations were considered, where the N–N axes are oriented either parallel or rotated by 45° wrt the $[001]/[\bar{1}10]$ directions. The resulting adsorption energies, computed for 3-layer slabs and large-core pseudopotentials, are shown in Figure 4. It appears that configurations with 0° azimuth placed on O_{2c} -row sites are largely favored (~ 1 eV) wrt the other ones, the bridge one being favored over the on-top by ~ 0.3 eV because of the stronger H-bond interaction. For 2H-TPP this difference is reduced to 0.2 eV because H-bonds are in general weaker. Our best estimates for adsorption energies, computed with 4-ML slabs and small-core pseudopotentials, are 5.31 eV and 3.41 eV for 4H-TPP and 2H-TPP, respectively.

Figure 4: Adsorption energy of 4H-TPP as a function of site and azimuthal orientation. Values are computed on 3ML slabs using a large-core pseudopotential for Ti (see text).

Theoretical calculations of core level shifts.

We estimated the the N 1s CLSs of the isolated 2H-TPP and the adsorbed 2H-TPP and 4H-TPP molecules by means of hybrid-DFT calculations, employing the PBE0 functional.¹⁰ Calculations were carried out with the ADF code.¹¹ Wavefunctions were expanded over a TZP basis set of Slater-type orbitals. Inner electrons of Ti, O, and C up to the 3*p*, 1*s* and 1*s* levels respectively, were treated as frozen cores, whereas all electrons pertaining to N atoms were allowed to relax. The scalar Zero Order Regular Approximation (ZORA)^{12,13} to the relativistic Hamiltonian was applied. Molecular clusters cut out from the optimized slab and properly saturated with H atoms were used as models for adsorbed molecules. In both the 2H-TPP and the 4H-TPP cases, the surface was represented as a Ti₃₁O₉₂H₆₀ cluster.

References

- (1) Floreano, L.; et al. Naletto, G.; Cvetko, D.; Gotter, R.; Malvezzi, M.; Marassi, L.; Morgante, A.; Santaniello, A.; Verdini, A.; Tommasini, F.; Tondello, G. *Rev. Sci. Instrum.* **1999**, *70*, 3855-3864.
- (2) Abadia, M.; Gonzalez-Moreno, R.; Sarasola, A.; Otero-Irureta, G.; Verdini, A.; Floreano, L.; Garcia-Lekue, A.; Rogero, C. *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2014**, *118*, 29704-29712.
- (3) Floreano, L.; Cossaro, A.; Gotter, R.; Verdini, A.; Bavdek, G.; Evangelista, F.; Ruocco, A.; Morgante, A.; Cvetko, D. *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2008**, *112*, 10794-10802.

- (4) Lanzilotto, V.; Lovat, G.; Otero, G.; Sanchez, L.; Lopez, M.F.; Mendez, J.; Martin-Gago, J.A.; Bavdek, G.; Floreano, L. *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2013**, *117*, 12639-12647.
- (5) Giannozzi, P. *et al.*, *J. Phys.: Condens. Matter* **2009**, *21*, 395502.
- (6) Perdew, J.; Burke, K.; Enzerhof, M. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **1996**, *77*, 3865-3868.
- (7) Grimme, S. *J. Comput. Chem.* **2006**, *27*, 1787-1799.
- (8) Barone, V.; Casarin, M.; Forrer, D.; Pavone, M.; Sambri, M.; Vittadini, A. *J. Comput. Chem.* **2009**, *30* 934-939.
- (9) D. Forrer, A. Vittadini, *Chem Phys. Lett.* **2011**, *516*, 72-75.
- (10) Adamo, C.; Barone, V. *J. Chem. Phys.* **1999**, *110*, 6158-6170.
- (11) Amsterdam Density Functional v. 2014 <http://www.scm.com/ADF>
- (12) van Lenthe, E.; Baerends, E. J.; Snijders, J.G. *J. Chem. Phys.* **1993**, *99*, 4597-4610.
- (13) van Lenthe, E.; Baerends, E. J.; Snijders, J.G. *J. Chem. Phys.* **1994**, *101*, 9783-9792.